

**ON q -ANALOG OF WOLSTENHOLME TYPE CONGRUENCES
FOR MULTIPLE HARMONIC SUMS**

Jianqiang Zhao

Department of Mathematics, Eckerd College, St. Petersburg, Florida
zhaoj8888@gmail.com

Received: 9/25/12, Accepted: 4/20/13, Published: 4/25/13

Abstract

Multiple harmonic sums are iterated generalizations of harmonic sums. Recently Dilcher has considered congruences involving q -analogs of these sums in depth one. In this paper we shall study the homogeneous case for arbitrary depth by using generating functions and shuffle relations of the q -analog of multiple harmonic sums. At the end, we also consider some non-homogeneous cases.

1. Introduction

In [8] Shi and Pan extended Andrews' result [1] on the q -analog of Wolstenholme Theorem to the following two cases: for all prime $p \geq 5$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{[j]_q} \equiv \frac{p-1}{2}(1-q) + \frac{p^2-1}{24}(1-q)^2 [p]_q \pmod{[p]_q^2}, \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{[j]_q^2} \equiv -\frac{(p-1)(p-5)}{12}(1-q)^2 \pmod{[p]_q}, \quad (2)$$

where $[n]_q = (1 - q^n)/(1 - q)$ for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $q \neq 1$. This type of congruences is considered in the polynomial ring $\mathbb{Z}[q]$ throughout this paper. Notice that the modulus $[p]_q$ is an irreducible polynomial in q when p is a prime. In [3] Dilcher generalized the above two congruences further to sums of the form $\sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{[j]_q^n}$ and $\sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \frac{q^n}{[j]_q^n}$ for all positive integers n in terms of certain determinants of binomial coefficients. However, his modulus is always $[p]_q$. He also expressed these congruences using Bernoulli numbers, Bernoulli numbers of the second kind, and Stirling numbers of the first kind, which we briefly recall now.

The well-known Bernoulli numbers are defined by the following generating series:

$$\frac{x}{e^x - 1} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n \frac{x^n}{n!} = 1 - \frac{1}{2} \frac{x}{1!} + \frac{1}{6} \frac{x^2}{2!} - \frac{1}{30} \frac{x^4}{4!} + \cdots$$

On the other hand, the Bernoulli numbers of the second kind are defined by the power series (cf. [7, p. 114]).

$$\frac{x}{\log(1+x)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_n \frac{x^n}{n!} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{x}{1!} - \frac{1}{6} \frac{x^2}{2!} + \frac{1}{4} \frac{x^3}{3!} - \frac{19}{24} \frac{x^4}{4!} + \dots$$

This is a little different from the definition of \tilde{b}_n in [3], which is changed to b_n later in the same paper. Finally, the Stirling numbers of the first kind $s(n, j)$ are defined by

$$x(x-1)(x-2)\cdots(x-n+1) = \sum_{j=0}^n s(n, j)x^j.$$

Define

$$K_n(p) := (-1)^{n-1} \frac{b_n}{n!} - \frac{(-1)^n}{(n-1)!} \sum_{j=1}^{[n/2]} \frac{B_{2j}}{2j} s(n-1, 2j-1)p^{2j}. \tag{3}$$

By [3, Thm. 1, (6.5) and Thm. 4] and [4, Thm. 3.1] one gets:

Theorem 1.1. *If $p > 3$ is a prime, then for all integers $n > 1$ we have*

$$\sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \frac{q^j}{[j]_q^n} \equiv K_n(p)(1-q)^n \pmod{[p]_q}.$$

We will need the following easy generalization of this theorem.

Theorem 1.2. *If $p > 3$ is a prime, then for every integer $n > t \geq 1$ we have*

$$\sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \frac{q^{tj}}{[j]_q^n} \equiv (1-q)^n \sum_{i=0}^{t-1} \binom{t-1}{i} (-1)^i K_{n-i}(p) \pmod{[p]_q}. \tag{4}$$

Moreover,

$$\sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{[j]_q^n} \equiv (1-q)^n \left(\frac{p-1}{2} + \sum_{j=2}^n K_j(p) \right) \pmod{[p]_q}. \tag{5}$$

Proof. If $t > 1$ it is clear that

$$q^{tj} = q^j (1 - (1 - q^j))^{t-1} = q^j \sum_{i=0}^{t-1} \binom{t-1}{i} (-1)^i (1 - q^j)^i.$$

So (4) follows from Theorem 1.1 immediately. Congruence (5) is a variation of [3, (5.11)]. □

All the sums in Theorem 1.1 and 1.2 are special cases of the q -analog of multiple harmonic sums. The congruence properties of the classical multiple harmonic sums (MHS for short) are systematically investigated in [10]. In this paper we shall study their q -analogs which are natural generalizations of the congruences obtained by Shi and Pan [8] and Dilcher [3].

Similar to its classical case (cf. [10]) a q -analog of multiple harmonic sum (q -MHS for short) is defined as follows. For $\mathbf{s} := (s_1, \dots, s_\ell) \in \mathbb{N}^\ell$, $\mathbf{t} := (t_1, \dots, t_\ell) \in \mathbb{N}^\ell$ and $n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ set

$$H_q^{(\mathbf{t})}(\mathbf{s}; n) := \sum_{1 \leq k_1 < \dots < k_\ell \leq n} \frac{q^{k_1 t_1 + \dots + k_\ell t_\ell}}{[k_1]_q^{s_1} \dots [k_\ell]_q^{s_\ell}}, \quad H_q^{*(\mathbf{t})}(\mathbf{s}; n) = H_q^{(\mathbf{t})}(\mathbf{s}; n) / (1 - q)^{w(\mathbf{s})}, \tag{6}$$

where $w(\mathbf{s}) := s_1 + \dots + s_\ell$ is the *weight*, $\ell(\mathbf{s}) := \ell$ the *depth* and \mathbf{t} the *modifier*. For trivial modifier we set

$$H_q(\mathbf{s}; n) := H_q^{(0, \dots, 0)}(\mathbf{s}; n), \quad H_q^*(\mathbf{s}; n) = H_q(\mathbf{s}; n) / (1 - q)^{w(\mathbf{s})}.$$

Note that in [3] $\tilde{H}_q(s; p - 1) := H_q^{(1)}(s; p - 1)$ are studied in some detail and are related to $H_q(s; p - 1)$. Also note that $H_q^{(s_1 - 1, \dots, s_\ell - 1)}(\mathbf{s}; n)$ are the partial sums of the most convenient form of q -multiple zeta functions (see [9]).

In this paper we mainly consider q -MHS with the trivial modifier. By convention we set $H_q^{(\mathbf{t})}(\mathbf{s}; r) = 0$ for $r = 0, \dots, \ell(\mathbf{s}) - 1$, and $H_q^{(\mathbf{t})}(\emptyset; n) = 1$. To save space, for an ordered set (e_1, \dots, e_t) we denote by $\{e_1, \dots, e_t\}^d$ the ordered set formed by repeating (e_1, \dots, e_t) d times. For example, $H_q(\{s\}^\ell; n)$ will be called a *homogeneous* sum.

Throughout the paper, we use short-hand $H_q(\mathbf{s})$ to denote $H_q(\mathbf{s}; p - 1)$ for some fixed prime p .

2. Homogeneous q -MHS

It is extremely beneficial to study the so-called *stuffle* (or *quasi-shuffle*) relations among MHS (see, for e.g., [10]). The same mechanism works equally well for q -MHS.

Recall that for any two ordered sets (r_1, \dots, r_t) and (r_{t+1}, \dots, r_n) the *shuffle* operation is defined by

$$\text{Shfl}((r_1, \dots, r_t), (r_{t+1}, \dots, r_n)) := \bigcup_{\substack{\sigma \text{ permutes } \{1, \dots, n\}, \\ \sigma^{-1}(1) < \dots < \sigma^{-1}(t), \\ \sigma^{-1}(t+1) < \dots < \sigma^{-1}(n)}} (r_{\sigma(1)}, \dots, r_{\sigma(n)}).$$

Fix a positive integer s . For any $k = 1, \dots, \ell - 1$, by *stuffle* relation we have

$$H_q^*((\ell - k)s) \cdot H_q^*({s}^k) = \sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \text{Shfl}(\{(\ell - k)s\}, \{s\}^k)} H_q^*(\mathbf{s}) + \sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \text{Shfl}(\{(\ell - k + 1)s\}, \{s\}^{k-1})} H_q^*(\mathbf{s}).$$

Applying $\sum_{k=1}^{\ell-1} (-1)^{\ell-k-1}$ on both sides we get

$$H_q^* (\{s\}^\ell) = \frac{1}{\ell} \sum_{k=0}^{\ell-1} (-1)^{\ell-k-1} H_q^* ((\ell - k)s) \cdot H_q^* (\{s\}^k). \tag{7}$$

Theorem 2.1. *Let s be a positive integer and let $\eta_s = \exp(2\pi\sqrt{-1}/s)$ be the s th primitive root of unity. Then*

$$\sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} H_q^* (\{s\}^\ell) x^\ell \equiv \frac{(-1)^s}{p^s x} \prod_{n=0}^{s-1} \left(1 - (1 - \eta_s^n (-x)^{1/s})^p\right) \pmod{[p]_q}.$$

Proof. Let $\zeta = \exp(2\pi\sqrt{-1}/p)$ be the primitive p th root of unity and set

$$P_n = \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{(1 - \zeta^j)^n}. \tag{8}$$

It is easy to see that $H_q^*(n) \equiv P_n \pmod{[p]_q}$. By using partial fractions Dilcher [4, (4.2)] obtained essentially the following generating function of P_n :

$$g(x) := \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P_n x^n = -\frac{px(x-1)^{p-1}}{1 - (1-x)^p}. \tag{9}$$

Let $a_\ell = H_q^* (\{s\}^\ell)$ for all $\ell \geq 0$. Let $w(x) = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} a_\ell x^\ell$ be its the generating function. By (7) we get

$$w(x) = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} a_\ell x^\ell \equiv 1 + \sum_{\ell=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\ell} \sum_{k=0}^{\ell-1} (-1)^{\ell-k-1} P_{(\ell-k)s} a_k x^\ell \pmod{[p]_q}.$$

Differentiating both sides and changing index $\ell \rightarrow \ell + 1$ we get, modulo $[p]_q$,

$$w'(x) \equiv \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^{\ell} (-1)^{\ell-k} P_{(\ell-k+1)s} a_k x^\ell \equiv \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{\ell=k}^{\infty} (-1)^{\ell-k} P_{(\ell-k+1)s} a_k x^\ell.$$

Changing index $\ell \rightarrow \ell + k$ and then exchanging the order of summation we get

$$\begin{aligned} w'(x) &\equiv w(x) \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} P_{(\ell+1)s} (-x)^\ell \equiv \frac{w(x)}{-x} \left(\sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} P_{\ell s} (-x)^\ell + 1 \right) \\ &\equiv \frac{w(x)}{-sx} \left(s + \sum_{n=0}^{s-1} \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} P_\ell (\eta_s^n (-x)^{1/s})^\ell \right) \\ &\equiv \frac{w(x)}{-sx} \left(s + \sum_{n=0}^{s-1} g(\eta_s^n (-x)^{1/s}) \right) \\ &\equiv \frac{w(x)}{-sx} \left(s - \sum_{n=0}^{s-1} \frac{p\eta^n (-x)^{1/s} (\eta^n (-x)^{1/s} - 1)^{p-1}}{1 - (1 - \eta_s^n (-x)^{1/s})^p} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Here $\eta_s = \exp(2\pi\sqrt{-1}/s)$ is the s th primitive root of unity. Thus

$$(\ln w(x))' = \left(-(\ln x)' + \sum_{n=0}^{s-1} \frac{(1 - (1 - \eta^n(-x)^{1/s})^p)'}{1 - (1 - \eta^n(-x)^{1/s})^p} \right).$$

Therefore by comparing the constant term we get

$$w(x) \equiv \frac{(-1)^s}{p^s x} \prod_{n=0}^{s-1} \left(1 - (1 - \eta^n(-x)^{1/s})^p \right) \pmod{[p]_q}$$

as desired. □

Corollary 2.2. *For every positive integer $\ell < p$ we have*

$$H_q(\{1\}^\ell) \equiv \frac{1}{\ell + 1} \binom{p-1}{\ell} \cdot (1-q)^\ell \pmod{[p]_q}.$$

Proof. By the theorem we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} H_q^*(\{1\}^\ell) x^\ell &\equiv \frac{(1+x)^p - 1}{px} \\ &\equiv \frac{1}{px} \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \binom{p}{\ell+1} x^{\ell+1} \equiv \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\ell+1} \binom{p-1}{\ell} x^\ell \pmod{[p]_q}. \end{aligned}$$

The corollary follows immediately. □

Corollary 2.3. *For every positive integer $\ell < p$ we have*

$$H_q(\{2\}^\ell) \equiv (-1)^\ell \frac{2 \cdot \ell!}{(2\ell+2)!} \binom{p-1}{\ell} \cdot F_{2,\ell}(p) \cdot (1-q)^{2\ell} \pmod{[p]_q},$$

where $F_{2,\ell}(p)$ is a monic polynomial in p of degree ℓ .

Proof. By Theorem 2.1 we have modulo $[p]_q$

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} H_q^*(\{2\}^\ell) x^\ell &\equiv \frac{1}{p^2 x} \left(1 - (1 - \sqrt{-1}\sqrt{x})^p \right) \left(1 - (1 + \sqrt{-1}\sqrt{x})^p \right) \\ &\equiv \frac{1}{p^2 x} \left| \sum_{j=1}^{(p-1)/2} \binom{p}{2j} (-1)^j x^j + \sqrt{-1}\sqrt{x} \sum_{j=0}^{(p-1)/2} \binom{p}{2j+1} (-1)^j x^j \right|^2, \end{aligned}$$

which easily yields

$$H_q^*(\{2\}^\ell) \equiv \frac{(-1)^\ell}{p^2} \left\{ \sum_{\substack{j+k=\ell \\ 0 \leq j, k < p/2}} \binom{p}{2j+1} \binom{p}{2k+1} - \sum_{\substack{j+k=\ell+1 \\ 1 \leq j, k < p/2}} \binom{p}{2j} \binom{p}{2k} \right\}.$$

In the first sum above if $j + k = \ell + 1$ and $1 \leq j, k < p/2$ then we may assume $j > \ell/2$. Then $(\ell + 1)! \binom{p}{\ell+1}$ is a factor of $(2j + 1)! \binom{p}{2j+1}$ as a polynomial of p , and so is $\ell!(p-1)$. Similarly we can see that $\ell!(p-1)$ is a factor of the second sum.

In order to determine the leading coefficient we set

$$C_1(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{\ell} \frac{(2\ell + 2)! x^{2j+1}}{(2j + 1)!(2\ell - 2j + 1)!} = \frac{(x + 1)^{2\ell+2} - (x - 1)^{2\ell+2}}{2},$$

$$C_2(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{\ell+1} \frac{(2\ell + 2)! x^{2j}}{(2j)!(2\ell - 2j + 2)!} = \frac{(x + 1)^{2\ell+2} + (x - 1)^{2\ell+2}}{2}.$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{\substack{j+k=\ell \\ 0 \leq j, k < p/2}} \frac{1}{(2j + 1)!(2k + 1)!} - \sum_{\substack{j+k=\ell+1 \\ 1 \leq j, k < p/2}} \frac{1}{(2j)!(2k)!} \\ &= \frac{C_1(1) - (C_2(1) - 2)}{(2\ell + 2)!} = \frac{2}{(2\ell + 2)!}. \end{aligned}$$

This finishes the proof of the corollary. □

Corollary 2.4. *Let ℓ be a positive integer. Set $\delta_\ell = (1 + (-1)^\ell)$ and $L = 3\ell + 3$. Then for every prime $p \geq L$ we have modulo $[p]_q$*

$$H_q(\{3\}^\ell) \equiv \begin{cases} \frac{-3 \cdot \ell!}{(3\ell + 1)!} \binom{p-1}{\ell} \cdot F_{3,\ell}(p) \cdot (1 - q)^{3\ell} & , \text{ if } \ell \text{ is odd,} \\ \frac{6 \cdot \ell!}{(3\ell + 3)!} \binom{p-1}{\ell} \cdot F_{3,\ell}(p) \cdot (1 - q)^{3\ell} & , \text{ if } \ell \text{ is even,} \end{cases} \tag{10}$$

where $F_{3,\ell}(p)$ is a monic polynomial in p of degree $2\ell - 1$ if ℓ is odd and of degree 2ℓ if ℓ is even.

Proof. Let $\eta = \exp(2\pi i/3)$. Then $\eta^2 + \eta + 1 = 0$. By Theorem 2.1 we have

$$\sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} H_q^*(\{3\}^\ell) x^\ell \equiv \frac{-1}{p^3 x} \prod_{a=0}^2 \left(1 - (1 - \eta^a \sqrt[3]{-x})^p \right). \tag{11}$$

We now use two ways to expand this. Set $y = \sqrt[3]{-x}$. First, the product on the right

hand side of (11) can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} & 1 - \sum_{a=0}^2 (1 - \eta^a y)^p + \sum_{a=0}^2 (1 - \eta^a y)^p (1 - \eta^{a+1} y)^p - \prod_{a=0}^2 (1 - \eta^a y)^p \\ &= 1 - \sum_{j=0}^p \binom{p}{j} \sum_{a=0}^2 \eta^{aj} y^j + \sum_{a=0}^2 (1 + \eta^a y + \eta^{a+1} y^2)^p - (1 + x)^p \\ &= 1 - 3 \sum_{j=0}^{\lfloor p/3 \rfloor} \binom{p}{3j} x^j + 3 \sum_{\substack{j,k \geq 0, j+k < p \\ 2j+k \equiv 0(3)}} \frac{p! (-x)^{(j+2k)/3}}{j! k! (p-j-k)!} - (1+x)^p. \end{aligned}$$

Thus for $\ell > 0$ we get

$$H_q^* (\{3\}^\ell) \equiv \frac{1}{p^3} \left\{ 3\delta_\ell \binom{p}{L} + (-1)^\ell \cdot 3 \sum_{k \geq 1} \binom{p}{L-k} \binom{L-k}{k} + \binom{p}{\ell+1} \right\}$$

Note that if ℓ is odd then the degree of the polynomial is reduced to $3\ell - 1$ with leading coefficient given by

$$(-1)^\ell \cdot 3 \frac{1}{(L-1)!} \binom{L-1}{1} = \frac{-3}{(L-2)!} = \frac{-3}{(3\ell+1)!}$$

as we wanted.

Now to prove $\ell! \binom{p}{\ell}$ is a factor we use the following expansion of (11):

$$\sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p^3 x} \sum_{j,k,n \geq 1} (-1)^{j+k+n} \binom{p}{j} \binom{p}{k} \binom{p}{n} x^{(j+k+n)/3} \eta^{k+2n}.$$

Thus

$$H_q^* (\{3\}^\ell) \equiv \frac{1}{p^3} \sum_{\substack{1 \leq j,k,n \leq p \\ j+k+n=3\ell+3}} (-1)^{j+k+n} \binom{p}{j} \binom{p}{k} \binom{p}{n} \eta^{k+2n} \pmod{[p]_q}.$$

Notice that $j + k + n = 3\ell + 3$ implies one of the indices, say j , is at least $\ell + 1$. Then clearly $\binom{p}{j}$ contains $\ell! \binom{p}{\ell}$ as a factor, therefore so does $H_q^* (\{3\}^\ell) \pmod{[p]_q}$. This completes the proof of the corollary. \square

3. Some Non-Homogeneous q -MHS Congruences

In this section we consider some non-homogeneous q -MHS of depth two with modifiers of special type.

Theorem 3.1. *Let m, n be two positive integers. For every prime p we have*

$$H_q^{(m,n)}(2m, 2n) \equiv \frac{1}{2} \{f(m; p)f(n; p) - f(m + n; p)\} \pmod{[p]_q}.$$

where

$$f(N; p) = (1 - q)^{2N} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \binom{N-1}{i} (-1)^i K_{2N-i}(p)$$

Proof. By definition and substitution $i \rightarrow p - i$ and $j \rightarrow p - j$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} H_q^{*(m,n)}(2m, 2n) &= \sum_{1 \leq i < j < p} \frac{q^{mi+nj}}{(1 - q^i)^{2m}(1 - q^j)^{2n}} \\ &= \sum_{1 \leq j < i < p} \frac{q^{pm+pn-mi-nj}}{(1 - q^{p-i})^{2m}(1 - q^{p-j})^{2n}} \\ &\equiv \sum_{1 \leq j < i < p} \frac{q^{mi+nj}}{(q^i - q^p)^{2m}(q^j - q^p)^{2n}} \pmod{[p]_q} \\ &\equiv \sum_{1 \leq j < i < p} \frac{q^{mi+nj}}{(1 - p^i)^{2m}(1 - p^j)^{2n}} \pmod{[p]_q} \\ &\equiv H_q^{*(n,m)}(2n, 2m) \pmod{[p]_q} \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

By shuffle relation we have

$$H_q^{*(m)}(2m)H_q^{*(n)}(2n) = H_q^{*(m,n)}(2m, 2n) + H_q^{*(n,m)}(2n, 2m) + H_q^{*(m+n)}(2m + 2n).$$

Together with (12) this yields

$$2H_q^{*(m,n)}(2m, 2n) \equiv H_q^{*(m)}(2m)H_q^{*(n)}(2n) - H_q^{*(m+n)}(2m + 2n) \pmod{[p]_q}.$$

Our theorem follows from (4) quickly. □

In the study of q -multiple zeta functions the following function appears naturally (see [9, (47)] or [2, Theorem 1]):

$$\varphi_q(n) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (k-1) \frac{q^{(n-1)k}}{[k]_q^n} = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{kq^{(n-1)k}}{[k]_q^n} - \zeta_q(n),$$

where $\zeta_q(n) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{q^{(n-1)k}}{[k]_q^n}$ is the q -Riemann zeta value defined by Kaneko et al. in [5]. Using the results we have obtained so far in this paper we discover a congruence related to the partial sums of $\varphi_q(2)$.

Proposition 3.2. *For every prime p we have*

$$\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{kq^k}{[k]_q^2} \equiv -\frac{p(p-1)(p+1)}{24} (1 - q)^2 \pmod{[p]_q}. \tag{13}$$

Proof. To save space, all congruences are modulo $[p]_q$ throughout this proof.

We can check the congruence (13) for $p = 2$ and $p = 3$ easily by hand. Now we assume $p \geq 5$. By definition we have

$$H_q^*(2, 1) = \sum_{1 \leq i < j < p} \frac{1}{(1 - q^i)^2(1 - q^j)}.$$

With the substitutions $i \rightarrow p - i$ and $j \rightarrow p - j$ we get

$$\begin{aligned} -H_q^*(2, 1) &= - \sum_{1 \leq j < i < p} \frac{q^{2i} \cdot q^j}{(q^i - q^p)^2(q^j - q^p)} \\ &\equiv - \sum_{1 \leq j < i < p} \frac{q^{2i} \cdot q^j}{(q^i - 1)^2(q^j - 1)} \\ &\equiv - \sum_{1 \leq j < i < p} \frac{(q^i - 1)^2 + 2(q^i - 1) + 1}{(q^i - 1)^2} \cdot \frac{1 - q^j - 1}{1 - q^j} \\ &\equiv H_q^*(1, 2) - 2H_q^*(1, 1) + \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{p - 3 + k}{1 - q^k} - \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{k - 1}{(1 - q^k)^2} - \binom{p - 1}{2} \\ &\equiv H_q^*(1, 2) - 2H_q^*(1, 1) + (p - 3)H_q^*(1) + H_q^*(2) \\ &\quad - \binom{p - 1}{2} - \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{kq^k}{(1 - q^k)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Notice that we have the stuffle relations

$$\begin{aligned} H_q^*(2, 1) + H_q^*(1, 2) &= H_q^*(1)H_q^*(2) - H_q^*(3), \\ 2H_q^*(1, 1) &= H_q^*(1)^2 - H_q^*(2). \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{kq^k}{(1 - q^k)^2} \equiv (H_q^*(1) + 2)H_q^*(2) - H_q^*(3) - H_q^*(1)^2 + (p - 3)H_q^*(1) - \binom{p - 1}{2}.$$

Notice that by [3, Theorem 2]

$$H_q^*(3) \equiv -\frac{(p - 1)(p - 3)}{8}. \tag{14}$$

The proposition now follows from (1) and (2) immediately. \square

4. A Congruence of Lehmer Type

Instead of the harmonic sums up to $(p-1)$ -st term Lehmer also studied the following type of congruence (see [6]): for every odd prime p

$$\sum_{j=1}^{(p-1)/2} \frac{1}{j} \equiv -2q_p(2) + q_p(2)^2 p \pmod{p^2},$$

where $q_p(2) = (2^{p-1} - 1)/p$ is the Fermat quotient. It is also easy to see that for every positive integer n and prime $p > 2n + 1$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{(p-1)/2} \frac{1}{j^{2n}} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}.$$

As a q -analog of the above we have

Theorem 4.1. *Let n be a positive integer. For every odd prime p we have*

$$H_q^{(n)}(2n; (p-1)/2) \equiv \frac{1}{2}(1-q)^{2n} \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{j} (-1)^j K_{2n-j}(p) \pmod{[p]_q}.$$

Proof. By definition and substitution $i \rightarrow p - i$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} H_q^{*(n)}(2n) &= H_q^{*(n)}(2n; (p-1)/2) + \sum_{1 \leq i \leq (p-1)/2} \frac{q^{n(p-i)}}{(1-q^{p-i})^{2n}} \\ &\equiv 2H_q^{*(n)}(2n; (p-1)/2) \pmod{[p]_q} \end{aligned}$$

which yields the theorem by (4) easily. □

To conclude the paper we remark that the congruence for general q -MHS should involve some type of q -analog of Bernoulli numbers and Euler numbers similar to the classical cases treated in [10]. We hope to return to this theme in the future.

Acknowledgement. This work is partly supported by the Faculty Development Fund of Eckerd College and the NSF grant DMS1162116.

References

- [1] G.E. Andrews, *q-analogs of the binomial coefficient congruences of Babbage, Wolstenholme and Glaisher*, Discrete Math., **204**(1) (1999), 15-25.

- [2] D.M. Bradley, *A q -analog of Euler's decomposition formula for the double zeta function*, Int. J. Math. Math. Sci., Vol. 2005, Issue 21, 2005, pp. 3453–3458.
- [3] K. Dilcher, *Determinant expressions for q -harmonic congruences and degenerate Bernoulli numbers*, Electron. J. Combin., **15**(1) (2008), R63.
- [4] F. T. Howard, *Explicit formulas for degenerate Bernoulli numbers*, Discrete Math. **162** (1996), 175–185.
- [5] M. Kaneko, N. Kurokawa, and M. Wakayama, *A variation of Euler's approach to values of the Riemann zeta function*, Kyushu J. Math. **57** (2003), 175–192.
- [6] E. Lehmer, *On congruences involving Bernoulli numbers and the quotients of Fermat and Wilson*, Ann. Math. **39** (1938), 350–360.
- [7] S. Roman, *The Umbral Calculus*, New York: Academic Press, 1984.
- [8] L.-L. Shi and H. Pan, *A q -analogue of Wolstenholme's harmonic series congruence*, Amer. Math. Monthly, **114**(6) (2007), 529–531.
- [9] J. Zhao, *Multiple q -zeta functions and multiple q -polylogarithms*, Ramanujan J., **14** (2)(2007), 189–221. arXiv: math/0304448
- [10] J. Zhao, *Wolstenholme type theorem for multiple harmonic sums*, Int. J. Number Theory, **4**(1) (2008), 73–106.